

M1.2 BFSP

Cross-Community workshop on Biodiversity, Food Security, and Pathogens

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

BFSP	Biodiversity, Food Security, and Pathogens
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats

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Executive Summary

The first cross-Community workshop for the Biodiversity, Food Security, and Pathogens (BFSP) Priority Area was held online on September the 12th 2024, from 09:00 to 13:00 CEST. The aim was to host a forum for information sharing and discussions to help foster interactions across ELIXIR Communities and Focus Groups in the BFSP domain, and to gather feedback on the draft organisation and contents of the BFSP Strategy being developed by the priority area co-leads. With almost 70 participants the forum successfully gathered together interested parties from across ELIXIR Nodes, Communities, and Focus Groups. The four selected projects from the first Open Call had the opportunity to present their plans to a wide audience, and the co-leads were able to gather valuable feedback to help shape the ongoing development of the BFSP Strategy.

Organisation of the Workshop

A four-hour virtual session was scheduled for the workshop on September 12th 2024. The event was announced in the monthly meetings of relevant ELIXIR Communities and Focus Groups, as well as being shared on relevant Slack channels and through ELIXIR mailing lists, the relevant events page can be found [here](#).

Participants were required to register for the workshop using the dedicated Eventscase registration system. A total of 66 participants registered to attend the workshop.

The workshop agenda (Table 1) was designed by the BFSP co-leads together with ELIXIR Hub support team members. The agenda was shared in advance of the workshop, and during the sessions participants were encouraged to contribute to collective note taking of the main points discussed.

Table 1: Workshop Agenda

Time	Activities
09:00-09:15	Introduction (Rob Waterhouse) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Personal presentations - asynchronous ● Tier objectives
09:15-10:00	BFSP Strategy Feedback (Cyril Pommier)
10:00-10:40 (10 min each)	Open Call project presentations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● E-PAN: enhancing pan-genome analysis in plants <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Michiel Van Bel ● FAIRyMAGs - Optimising Metagenomics Assembled Genomes building: workflow finalisation, training material development, real data evaluation, and resource allocation tool creation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Paul Zierrep ● HARVEST: Handling and alignment of plant research FAIRification - value through the use of ELIXIR data Standards and Tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sebastian Beier ● Odyssey: Connecting molecular and geographical biodiversity data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Aristotelis Papageorgiou
10:40-10:55	Break
10:55-11:55	Inter-Communities Collaborations (Tereza Manousaki)
11:55-12:00	Bio-Break

FAIRification - value through the use of ELIXIR data Standards and Tools; and [4] Odyssey: Connecting molecular and geographical biodiversity data. This was an opportunity for the project members to present their project's aims and objectives, as well as briefly describe their proposed approaches and answer questions from the participants.

In the third main part the focus was on how to foster better inter-Community (and Focus Group) interactions connected to the BFSP domain. This was achieved by first briefly presenting the main relevant Communities and Focus Groups (Biodiversity, Plant Sciences, Microbiome, Pathogens, Domestic Animals Genome and Phenome), and then by working together in smaller Zoom breakout rooms, each with a moderator to facilitate the discussions. Participants in each breakout room noted discussion points in the slidedeck¹. The main topics where inter-Community collaborations could be further developed to support the growth of BFSP-related activities in ELIXIR.

As the discussions were very engaging and fruitful they took slightly longer than planned, so the fourth main part dedicated to making connections to external consortia/projects was condensed - with a reminder of the importance of also looking outwards, and a request to continue to populate a collection of such consortia/projects that was first launched in June at the ELIXIR All Hands meeting in the BSFP Mini Symposium.

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¹ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1VAzzW8l46aYvuDcfLVyav1gVFyXJAden/view?usp=sharing>

Outcomes and Impacts of the Milestone

The workshop successfully gathered together almost 70 participants with interests connected to research in the BFSP domain. The forum provided participants with the opportunity to understand what has been developed in the BFSP Priority Area to date, and to contribute to shaping the BFSP Strategy. Discussions were fruitful, both for the co-leads to receive input from a broad audience, and for the Communities and Focus Groups to be stimulated to start considering synergies in the BFSP domain. A consideration for future actions would be to ensure that the ELIXIR Platforms are better integrated into contributing to the development of the BFSP Priority Area and Strategy. The co-leads can use these outcomes to refine and further develop the BFSP Strategy, ensuring that the scope, mission, objectives, etc. are all well-aligned with a consensus from across ELIXIR members.

Dissemination Plans

While the outcomes of this milestone's workshop remain for internal use, they feed directly into the development of the BFSP Strategy, which will be disseminated using either Zenodo or F1000.